

EFFECTIVENESS OF GOVERNMENT SUPPORT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE LIVESTOCK SECTOR

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Annotatio: *On the basis of the adopted regulatory legal acts on the further development of the livestock industry, the issues of increasing the efficiency of state support for the livestock industry were analyzed using the example of entrepreneurs in the livestock industry and summed up.*

Key words:

Introduction: *One of the most pressing issues today is the accelerated development of the livestock sector, the introduction of modern and innovative methods in the field, increasing the volume and variety of products, as well as further expanding the scope of work to provide the population with quality and affordable livestock products is calculated.*

Of course: *the effective support of the state in solving these problems in the field of animal husbandry is of paramount importance.*

Literature review. The issues of improving the efficiency of the agricultural economy, agro-industrial complex and the livestock sector and the production of its various products have been studied in detail by domestic and foreign agro-economists. In particular, scientists of our country TS Mallaboev, RR Radjapov, Q. Cho-riev, A. Juraev, NS Bazarov, S. Mekhmanov, KD Mirzaev, JH Rashidov, R. Hakimov, T.Kudratov, R.Kh.Ergashev, S.R.Khalikov developed proposals to increase livestock production and increase its efficiency in meeting the demand of the population for livestock products in Uzbekistan. Also, the proposals and recommendations developed as a result of research conducted by foreign scientists GA Avanesova, I.A.Altukhin, V.I.Gayduk, F.Kotler, P.G.A.Jennings serves as an important theoretical and methodological guide in the development of the text, increasing production and increasing the efficiency of the industry.

In the development of the livestock sector in the development of the service sector AR Baycherova development of veterinary services in the regions with differentiation depending on the level of development of the livestock sector; Sh.A. Jantemirov, A.Sh. Jantemirova and Artyomova EI Organization of clusters on product types and directions in the innovative development of the livestock sector; LI Kovalev Development of technical services in the livestock sector; KJ Mirzaev in his research

work developed scientific and practical proposals and recommendations for the organization of agroservice in animal husbandry.

Research methodology.

Further development of the livestock sector in the country, the introduction of modern and innovative methods in the field, the introduction of a cluster system for livestock development, increasing food production and processing and expanding the range of food security and government support. The normative-legal documents adopted on the subject were studied and their implementation was analyzed in detail. Scientific research has been studied in the country, using methods such as grouping, comparison, analysis and synthesis, observation.

Analysis and discussion of results.

At present, a number of measures are being taken in the country to strengthen the material and technical base of specialized livestock farms, modernize the production process, strengthen and update the feed base, reduce costs, increase the volume and improve the quality of products.

In this regard, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 18, 2019 No PQ-4243 "On measures to further develop and support the livestock sector", the Presidential Decree of January 29, 2020 "On measures to support the livestock sector", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5017 of March 3, 2021 "On additional measures for further state support of the livestock sector" and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2022 Resolution No. PQ-120 "On approval of the program for the development of the livestock sector and its branches in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2022 - 2026". These resolutions set the task of overcoming the problems in the livestock sector and raising the livestock sector to a new level through the use of modern technologies and practices, as well as ensuring cooperation between farms, as well as livestock processing enterprises and livestock businesses. Accelerated development of the livestock sector, the introduction of modern and innovative methods in the field, increasing the volume and variety of products, as well as the uninterrupted supply of the population with quality and affordable livestock products, attracting investment from foreign and domestic investors. with the support of the state.

Of course, all these tasks are set by the state to ensure food security and accelerate the development of the livestock sector in the country, improve the selection and breeding of livestock, nutrition, implementation of modern, innovative ideas in animal husbandry, increase livestock production and provide the population with quality and affordable products. as well as strengthening the fodder base in animal husbandry, the work carried out by the state to provide economic support to farms specializing in animal husbandry.

Today, there are a total of 18,032 livestock farms in the country, of which 7,614 are cattle, 3,263 sheep and goats, 142 horses, 52 camels, 1,163 poultry, 4,829 fisheries;

715 bees and 254 rabbits. In the livestock sector alone, the number of farms with 500 to 1,000 head of livestock increased to 256, and the number of farms with 1,000 and more head of livestock reached 136. In 2021, all categories of farms are being cared for 91.8% of cattle (95.5% in 2018) fell to households, and 8.2% (4.5% in 2018) to farms. The production of meat products per capita reached 47.5 kilograms (annual norm - 46.1 kilograms per capita), dairy products - 336 kilograms (annual norm per capita - 310.4 kilograms). In 2021, 2.4 million cows and carcasses kept in households and farms were artificially inseminated, and the number of improved breeds reached 54%. In addition, new breeds of beef cattle were imported from abroad, such as Aberdeen-Angus, Sharole, Gereford and Limousin, and dairy breeds such as Jersey, Schwitz and Montbilliards. In particular, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Jizzakh, Navoi, Syrdarya, Tashkent, Khorezm regions more than 100 thousand of such breeds are cared for. Merinos, Romanov, Edilboy, Dorper breeds of sheep and Angor and Zanen breeds of goats were also imported to improve the breed and increase the productivity of small cattle. At the same time, a total of 497 livestock breeding farms were transferred to the breeding category, bringing their number to 1,640. In 2021, of the 339.7 thousand hectares of land allocated to livestock for the cultivation of food crops, 37 thousand hectares of new alfalfa (100 thousand hectares contain old alfalfa), 158.5 thousand hectares of corn for silage, 31.8 thousand hectares of white corn, 13.8 thousand thousand hectares were planted with beetroot. In addition, a total of 23.8 million tons of fodder was stored on 177,400 hectares of vacant land to strengthen the fodder base for livestock. However, the number of head of livestock is 2.5 times higher than the norm of allocated arable land (average 0.5-0.6 hectares per conditional head of livestock). Although there is a possibility to accumulate 10-12 tons of nutrients per hectare of arable land allocated for food crops, 6-7 tons of nutrients are accumulated per hectare.

Conclusions and suggestions.

The emergence of interdependence in the livestock sector will lead to increased production of livestock products, the introduction of recycling, meeting the demand of the population for livestock products and further increasing the export potential. At the same time, the state support of the livestock sector, along with the introduction of modern and innovative methods in animal husbandry, will increase the volume of production and expand the range of products, which will reduce the cost of production. The results of the study provided the basis for formulating the following recommendations.

- 100% state guarantees for foreign investment in animal husbandry and tenders among entrepreneurs for the investment;
- conducting tenders among entrepreneurs on investments in animal husbandry at the expense of state, commercial banks and established funds;

- setting the state funding of the percentage of loans received by commercial banks from entrepreneurs for the development of the livestock sector above the refinancing rate of the Central Bank.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the state support for the rapid and effective development of the livestock sector in the country helps to quickly solve the financial and economic difficulties of livestock farms and provide the population with quality and affordable livestock products, the introduction of modern technologies in animal husbandry, modernize the production process and solve a number of problems that hinder the expansion of exports of finished livestock products.

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